

Notes

Search for Potential Amoebicides II, Synthesis of Substituted (-Sulphazino) Quinolines

V. S. MISRA & V. K. SAXENA

Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University, Lucknow

Manuscript received 20 February 1973; revised 14 May 1974;
accepted 23 July 1974

A large number of quinoline derivatives occupy an important place as antiamoebic agents which include some of the most effective and best tolerated amoebicides known so far¹⁻⁶. A comparative study of the amoebicidal quinolines reveals that the quinoline moieties having a methoxy or a methyl substituent (at position 8) in the benzene ring of the nucleus are the most effective.

It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to synthesise such substituted quinoline derivatives containing a sulphazino or substituted sulphazino ring. This was effected by diazotizing an appropriate amine (1-a-d) and treating the diazotised solution with substituted 4-hydroxy, 3-methyl, 2-carboethoxy or carboxy, 8-methoxy or methyl quinolines and 4-hydroxy, 2-carboethoxy, 8-methoxy or methyl quinolines (2-a-e): thus yielding seventeen substituted (-sulphazino) quinolines (3-a-q) (cf. Table 1). It is well known that this coupling of diazotised aniline with 8-hydroxy quinoline⁸⁻¹² and 8-amino quinoline¹³⁻¹⁴ takes place at position 5. Recently some workers^{17,19} have coupled diazotised sulphonamides with 8-hydroxy quinoline and they too have indicated that diazo coupling occurs at position 5. On the basis of these earlier observations it has been assumed by the present authors that the coupling of diazotised

1	R ₁	2	R ₈	R ₂	3	R ₁	R ₈	R ₂
a	-1,3-diazino	a	-OCH ₃	-COOEt	a	-1,3-diazino	-OCH ₃	-COOEt
b	-guanidino	b	-CH ₃	-COOEt	b	-guanidino	-OCH ₃	-COOEt
c	-H	e	-OCH ₃	-COOH	c	-H	-OCH ₃	-COOH
d	-thiazolino				d	-H	-OCH ₃	-COOEt
					e	-thiazolino	-OCH ₃	-COOEt
					f	-H	-CH ₃	-COOEt
					g	-thiazolino	-CH ₃	-COOEt
					h	-guanidino	-CH ₃	-COOEt
					i	-1,3-diazino	-CH ₃	-COOEt

1	-R ₁	2	-R ₈	3	-R ₁	-R ₈
a	-1,3-diazino	c	-OCH ₃	j	-thiazolino	-OCH ₃
b	-guanidino	d	-OCH ₃	k	-guanidino	-OCH ₃
c	-H			l	-H	-OCH ₃
d	-thiazolino			m	-1,3-diazino	-OCH ₃
				n	-1,3-diazino	-CH ₃
				o	-thiazolino	-CH ₃
				p	-H	-CH ₃
				q	-guanidino	-CH ₃

sulphonamides with 8-methoxy and 8-methyl quinolines also occurs at position 5 and not at position 7 (3-a-i). Out of these nine were tested for amoebicidal activity against *Entamoeba histolytica*.

Bio-assay

Nine representative compounds, 3-a-i given in Table 1 were tested for their amoebicidal property against *Entamoeba histolytica* (axenic), and the results are given below :

Compound No.	Amoebicidal and point ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
3-a	Nil
3-b	Nil
3-c	1 : 32,000
3-d	1 : 16,000
3-e	Nil
3-f	1 : 8,000
3-g	Nil
3-h	Nil
3-i	1 : 16,000
Emetine HCl	1 : 128,000

As seen above the maximum activity is shown by 3c i.e.,

which is the simplest molecule out of all the synthesised ones.

Experimental

Sulphadrigs (1, a-d) were isolated by known methods¹⁵⁻¹⁶. The quinolines (2, a-e) were prepared according to the procedure cited in the literature⁷.

The diazotization¹⁷⁻¹⁸ was affected by the following method :

The appropriate sulphadrig (1.25 g) was dissolved in dilute HCl (5 ml of conc. HCl+5 ml of water). To the cooled hydrochloride solution, sodium nitrite (4 g in 15 ml of water) was gradually added at 0°-5°.

The diazotized solution was added dropwise to the ice cooled solution of the appropriate hydroxy quinoline in NaOH (1.0 g in 25% NaOH solution). After the addition was complete, the solution was kept in a refrigerator overnight; acidified with HCl, filtered and crystallised from ethanol.

The analytical data, m.p.'s and yields are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	m.p. °C ^a	Yield %	Molecular Formula	% S	
				Found	Calcd.
3a	199	60	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₅ N ₆ S	6.86	6.13
3b	210	70	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₅ N ₆ S	7.23	6.58
3c	220	40	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₆ N ₄ S	7.51	7.69
3d	230d	50	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₄ S	6.84	7.20
3e	185	80	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₆ S ₂	12.14	12.78
3f	188	69	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₄ S	6.94	7.47
3g	200	45	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₆ S ₂	12.52	13.01
3h	205	35	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₅ N ₆ S	6.72	6.80
3i	230(d)	65	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₅ N ₆ S	7.21	6.32
3j	210	70	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₅ N ₅ S ₂	12.46	12.66
3k	220	80	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₆ S	7.36	6.77
3l	250	55	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₆ N ₄ S	8.32	7.44
3m	260(d)	40	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₆ S	5.84	6.29
3n	240	50	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₆ S	7.24	6.50
3o	200	60	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₅ N ₅ S ₂	12.87	12.87
3p	210(d)	65	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₅ N ₄ S	7.62	7.72
3q	220	70	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₆ S	7.88	7.01

a) m.p.'s are uncorrected.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. Nitya Nand, Scientist Incharge, C.D.R.I., Lucknow (Medicinal Chemistry Division) for getting the bioassay work done and to the Head of the Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University for providing the necessary facilities. One of them (V.K.S.) is thankful to the C.S.I.R., for the award of a junior research fellowship.

References

1. J. H. OSBOND, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 1853.
2. J. H. BURCKHALTER and W. H. EDGERTON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4838.
3. N. J. CONAN, *Amer. J. Trop. Med. Hyg.*, 1951, 31, 18; *J. Med. Chem.*, 1949, 6, 309.
4. D. H. R. BARTON, W. S. LINNELL and H. SENIOR, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 436.
5. VON OETTINGEN, "The Therapeutic Agents on the Quinoline Group", Chemical Cat. Co., New York, 1933.
6. O. MAGIDSON *et al.*, *Z. Obsc. Chim.*, 1937, 7.
7. E. A. STECK, L. H. HALLOCK and J. HOLLAND, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 131.
8. MATHEUS, *Ber.*, 1888, 21, 1642, 1886.
9. WOROTSTBEZOW and KOGAN, *Ber.*, 1930, 63, 2354.
10. KOGAN, *Ber.*, 1931, 64, 2150.
11. TSUNEO MATSUO, AKIHIKO MUSASHI and YOSHIHIKO NAITO, *J. Pharma. Soc.*, Japan, 1952, 1456.
12. EUGENE SAWICK, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, 22, 743.
13. JACOBS and HEIDELBERGER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 2273; 1922, 44, 1077.
14. RESHAW, FRIEDMAN and GAJEWSKI, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 3322.

NOTES

15. BRITISH PHARMACOPEIA, 1963, 781.
 16. BRITISH PHARMACOPEIA, 1953, 541, 543, 546.
 17. R. E. HARMON and B. L. GELLER, S. K. GUPTA, M. H. HERBERT and D. CHITRANJAN, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1970, 59, 1031.
 18. R. E. HARMON, E. F. DUTTON and H. D. WARREN, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1968, 11, 627.
 19. MATSUNAGA and YOSHIO, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1971, 44, 878

Potential anticonvulsant drugs—Part II.

Synthesis of Succinimido/Phthalimido Butyryl Ureas and Thioureas

VINAY S. MISRA & SHIV PRAKASH

Department of Chemistry, University of Lucknow, Lucknow

Manuscript received 8 August 1973; revised 16 August 1974; accepted 20 August 1974

DECREASE in the availability of γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA) in the central nervous system has been established¹⁻³ to be one of the reasons behind convulsive disorders. α -Ethyl- α -methyl succinimido is reported to be effective⁴⁻⁵ as an anticonvulsant agent. Phenyl urea derivatives have also been shown to possess significant anticonvulsant properties⁶⁻¹⁴.

On the basis of these observations a number of *N*-(γ -succinimido/ γ -phthalimido)-butyryl-*N'*-aryl ureas and thioureas have been designed. In the present communication synthesis of these compounds and their efficacy as anticonvulsants are reported.

γ -Phthalimido butyric acid, γ -phthalimido butyryl chloride and aryl ureas were obtained by procedures described in the literature¹⁵⁻¹⁷.

(a) γ -Succinimido butyric acid

Succinic anhydride (10 g, 0.01 mole) and γ -amino-butyric acid (10.3 g, 0.01 mole) were fused for 30 mins. at 120° in an oil bath. The crude product obtained on cooling was recrystallised from benzene, m.p. 90°. Yield 14.8 g (80%). Anal. calculated for C, H and N : C, 51.89%; H, 5.94; N, 7.53. Found : C, 52.4%; H, 5.45; N, 7.44. I.R. C-N: 3250 cm⁻¹; C=O : 1680 cm⁻¹ C=O : 1760 cm⁻¹.

(b) γ -Succinimido butyryl chloride :

In a two necked flask equipped with a reflux condenser a guard tube, and a dropping funnel, were placed γ -succinimido butyric acid (9.25 g.) and dry chloroform (40 ml.). Thionyl chloride (6.5 g) was slowly added with occasional stirring. The reaction mixture was then warmed on a water bath for 4 hrs. The excess of thionyl chloride and chloroform were removed under reduced pressure. The solid product thus obtained was used for further reactions without purification.

(c) *N*-(γ -succinimido/ γ -phthalimido)-butyryl-*N'*-Aryl ureas :

A mixture of (γ -succinimido/ γ -phthalimido)-butyryl chloride (0.001 mole), dry chloroform/benzene (10 ml), and appropriate aryl ureas was refluxed on a steam bath for 6-7 hrs. At the end of this period the solvent was removed under reduced pressure, residue extracted with water and recrystallised from ethanol.

The analysis, m.p. and other data are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

III-R = Succinimido
 IV-R = Phthalimido

Sl. No.	R	R ¹	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	% N	
					Calcd.	Found
1.	Succinimido	H	185	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄	13.86	13.45
2.	"	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	205	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄	13.25	12.94
3.	"	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	210	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄	13.25	13.02
4.	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	216	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄	13.25	12.99
5.	"	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	225	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅	12.61	12.12
6.	"	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	235	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅	12.61	12.04
7.	"	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	240	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅	12.61	12.26
8.	"	<i>p</i> -Cl	185	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄ Cl	12.42	12.32
9.	Phthalimido	H	218	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄	11.96	11.89
10.	"	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	230	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄	11.83	11.80
11.	"	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	175	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄	11.83	11.78
12.	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	210	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄	11.83	11.74
13.	"	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	261	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅	11.02	10.98
14.	"	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	280	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅	11.02	10.94
15.	"	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	270	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅	11.02	10.96
16.	"	<i>p</i> -Cl	194	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄ Cl	10.86	10.76

(a) All the melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected.
 (b) These compounds were obtained in 65-75% yields.